

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Evaluating soil structure

Soil structure is the spatial organization of soil particles (sand, clay, silt and organic matter). A well-structured soil will have c.a. 50% of pore space and c.a. 50% of that will be large pores (i.e. 50% solids, 25% water pores, 25% air pores). In addition, the pores should be continuous, allowing good water and gas transport and little resistance for root growth. In the microscale, the soil should be aggregated: the soil particles should form spongy groups which have internal porosity.

Measuring pore volume or aggregate sizes can be done in a soil laboratory, but for practical applications, soil structure evaluation can be more useful. In evaluating soil structure, visual observations are made and combined to an overall assessment. Usually the analysis is done by taking a small part of soil and breaking it with hands to see how it crumbles. A soil, which is easy to crumble into porous small aggregates is much better

structured than a soil which breaks into large angular blocks. Visual evaluation of soil structure (VESS) makes this into a more detailed analysis.

The VESS test is a form of spade-analysis: a block of soil is dug up with a shovel (20-30 cm deep, 20 cm wide, c.a. 5-10 cm thick, from an undisturbed side of a soil trench). The shovel profile is split into layers and each layer is scored using a VESS-chart which has indicators for classes from good (1 point) to bad structure (5 point). After scoring all the layers, the scores are averaged weighted by the soil layer thickness. Scores of 4 and over indicate serious compaction, which may need loosening.

4-5 VESS tests should be done on each field to see how the structure varies and which parts of the field might need extra work. It is an easy method, which can provide valuable insights.

1. A soil profile can reveal much about the farming practices and soil structure.

KEYWORDS

Soil structure, monitoring, spade diagnosis, physical soil health

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